

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO PRESCHOOL EDUCATION CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article discusses the benefits of early foreign language learning for children, highlighting its significance in fostering their development, expanding their worldview, and nurturing them into knowledgeable, intelligent, and broad-minded individuals who are well-equipped to become valuable professionals for society and the nation. Furthermore, the article emphasizes that incorporating engaging, beneficial, and effective foreign language instruction in preschool settings lays the groundwork for nurturing multilingual, broad-minded professionals capable of handling multiple tasks simultaneously.

Key words: Foreign languages, skills, creativity, multimedia, picture drawing, travel lesson, productive, creative thinking;

Currently, not only school, lyceum students and university students, but also preschool children are being taught foreign languages, especially English. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally advanced nations is a key factor in accessing the achievements of global science and progress.

Language acquisition is also linked to age. Psychologists believe that children learn languages faster and more easily than adults. The natural inclination of children to learn languages and their strong imitative abilities are key reasons behind this. However, there are considerable challenges involved in teaching languages to young children. Preschoolers lack the logical reasoning or comparative learning abilities of adults. They primarily memorize and visualize what they see. Therefore, teaching foreign languages to young children is a demanding task requiring considerable skill and responsibility.

Teaching preschool children a language requires exceptional skill and creativity from educators. When introducing foreign languages to children of this age, it is crucial to utilize diverse, engaging, and interactive methods that stimulate their thinking, rather than relying on a single teaching approach. Lessons should ideally be kept to a maximum of 15 minutes to avoid boring the children.

There are various methods for delivering engaging and effective lessons. We will highlight a few of them.

1. Teaching English through songs and poems.

Teaching through songs and poems helps children learn difficult letters or words by incorporating them into melodies. For example, you can utilize various short, engaging foreign language songs suitable for children. Creating a flexible classroom environment is sometimes more important than any teaching method. At the beginning of the class, the teacher can start with an enjoyable English song and have all the children sing along, even dancing a bit to the rhythm. This naturally strengthens their bodies, helps them become more alert, and promotes faster memorization of the song lyrics. English poems and songs naturally contribute to a good learning atmosphere. Children have limited self-control and difficulty maintaining focus throughout the entire lesson. Therefore, teachers should prioritize teaching songs, poems, or tongue twisters that engage children's listening skills.

2. Teaching foreign language through multimedia.

We often encounter a lack of foreign language listening skills in preschool children, indicating that they have not received sufficient auditory learning experiences. In real life, we might see our children silently watching cartoons under the television. It is essential to regularly expose kindergarten students to foreign language cartoons. Developing foreign language skills from an early age can facilitate the child's easy understanding of all knowledge later on. While children may not fully comprehend the words in a foreign language cartoon, they try to understand the words used by observing the characters' actions. Language development during the preschool stage is primarily shaped through constant imitation, with many roles emerging primarily through mimicking cartoons. Therefore, we can observe changes in children's behavior while watching cartoons. Considering these factors, cartoons, songs, and various video clips can be considered fun and effective ways for children to learn a language. For this reason, it is time to equip kindergartens with advanced technology. Currently, some parents are concerned about their children's interest in cartoons. In reality, cartoons broaden children's worldviews and play a crucial role in developing their imagination.

Additionally, smaller group sizes are better in language learning settings. When the educator consistently tailors their teaching methods to the individual psychology of each child, they need to be more than just a teacher; they also

need to be an artist, musician, foreign language instructor, and a skilled psychologist.

3. Teaching foreign languages through drawing.

Young children enjoy drawing various types of pictures, coloring them, and engaging in many other delightful activities during lessons. Teaching foreign languages through drawing and coloring can be highly effective for children. When a teacher conducts a lesson by having children draw, they not only teach English but also nurture the child's creative potential. The great artist Pablo Picasso famously said, "Every child is an artist." This highlights the importance of bringing out the latent abilities in children. We must allow them to express their creativity. They learn English by being told the names, shapes, and colors of the objects in their drawings. Alternatively, they can choose a theme and draw a picture about it under the guidance of the teacher, then discuss it. This is why drawing is a required skill for kindergarten teachers and educators in some foreign countries, particularly in China. Encourage children to be creative, and you will witness the birth of great works and their ascent to new heights.

Another important thing for teachers to remember is to never put pressure on children. There's no need to force them; simply engage them in the lesson. Young children learn foreign languages more easily than adults. It's not necessary to correct every mistake they make. They learn to speak even if they make mistakes, and those mistakes can be corrected later. Otherwise, they might develop a fear of speaking the language.

2. Teaching through travel lessons

Not only young children, but also adults, are more likely to remember what they learn when they can see, touch, and feel it, rather than simply imagining it. Confucius, the Chinese philosopher and founder of Confucianism, said centuries ago: "I hear and I forget. I see and I remember. I do and I understand." Therefore, it is more effective to bring children into the actual environment rather than forcing them to just imagine it while sitting in a classroom. Field trips allow children to experience the world they are learning about firsthand. For example, when discussing the spring season, you can take the children to the kindergarten's yard and teach them the names of natural changes, leaves, flowers, birds, and other things in English. Or, if you want to talk about animals, you can take them to the zoo and teach them the names, colors, sizes, and shapes of each animal. Words learned through such field trips are etched in a child's memory for a lifetime. Recent studies have shown that after two weeks, people remember 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see,

50% of what they see and hear, 70% of what they say, and 90% of what they say and do. Therefore, field trips are very beneficial for young children. Information learned through imagination while sitting in a classroom fades quickly, but words learned by seeing, touching, feeling, or performing actions themselves are never forgotten. Consequently, it is safe to say that the wider application of such methods in preschool institutions would be beneficial.

It is sometimes observed that educators fail to achieve the desired results. One of the main reasons for this could be their ineffective use of question-and-answer techniques. Many preschool children are less talkative and tend to be indifferent towards things they don't enjoy. Overcoming this requires significant effort from the educator.

The questions posed by the educator should demonstrate their wisdom and thorough understanding of the topic. Additionally, it is scientifically proven that children's sensory organs are significantly more developed than those of adults. While they may not be able to express it verbally, they still feel it and demonstrate it through their behavior. This insight suggests that the question-and-answer process can be divided into several parts:

I. Removing barriers between the educator and the learner: This approach allows the educator to connect with the children on a deeper level. A gentle approach to the question-and-answer process is essential.

II. The educator must be able to ask questions that consider the emotional and cognitive development of each child. This requires them to tailor their questions to the individual's language level. Even among preschoolers, subtle differences in language ability can be observed.

III. Asking more questions about previously covered topics: This helps build confidence and reduces anxiety. Before introducing new topics, it is essential to prepare them by asking questions about familiar subjects, ensuring they feel comfortable with the new material.

IV. Encouraging children: Recent research suggests that children under 12 years old are not receptive to criticism but respond positively to encouragement, leading to better outcomes. Therefore, encouraging every child's response, regardless of its correctness, can be a powerful way to inspire them.

In conclusion, childhood can be considered the most crucial stage for nurturing a person's cognitive abilities. Therefore, educators in school settings should prioritize teaching methodologies that resonate with children's interests. Fostering creativity and intellectual development through innovative multimedia technologies, modern teaching strategies, and engaging activities

that enhance auditory perception, color recognition, and shape identification is essential. These methods can significantly contribute to improving children's information processing skills and cultivate multifaceted thinking. Teaching language to young children should be approached as an engaging activity rather than a chore. Employing multiple effective methods in the learning process can lay a strong foundation for their future knowledge acquisition. Therefore, it is crucial for preschoolers to acquire excellent knowledge, develop their cognitive and creative thinking abilities, and cultivate the ability to express their thoughts independently and confidently. After all, the children we educate today are our future

References:

1. Elkonin, D.B. Psychology of Play. Moscow, 1978.
2. Ekaterina Stoops, PhD Professor of Education, A Personal Approach to Teaching Foreign Languages to Children from an Early Age. Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern Trends in the Development of Preschool and Primary Education"
3. O. Khoshimov, I. Yoqubov Methodology of Teaching English. Tashkent: 2003 - 270 p.
4. Ganiev A. Abdunazarova Z. Biophysics of brain activity. Brain activity in the development of "creative thinking" "mind map". Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT) P. 3 2021.